

Supplementary Table 1. Human RNAseq and qPCR validation data. Results $2^{-(dct)}$

RNASeq	qPCR	HCON	HEND	HRES	Significance
hsa-let-7a-3p					
hsa-let-7a-5p	hsa-let-7a-5p	0.00097858	0.01257951	0.00510173	>0.05
hsa-let-7b-3p					
hsa-let-7b-5p	hsa-let-7b-5p	0.00282114	0.00044773	0.00038481	>0.05
hsa-let-7c-5p	hsa-let-7c-5p	0.00021997	0.00107559	0.00360515	>0.05
hsa-let-7d-3p					
hsa-let-7d-5p					
hsa-let-7e-5p					
hsa-let-7f-1-3p					>0.05
hsa-let-7f-5p	hsa-let-7f-5p	0.0003892	0.00091421	0.0022275	(0.077)
hsa-let-7g-5p					
hsa-let-7i-3p					
hsa-let-7i-5p	hsa-let-7i-5p	0.00140092	0.00070679	0.00162834	>0.05
hsa-miR-1					
hsa-miR-100-5p					>0.05
hsa-miR-101-3p	hsa-miR-101-3p	0.00124234	0.00063347	0.00042469	(0.064)
hsa-miR-101-5p					
hsa-miR-103a-3p					
hsa-miR-106b-3p					
hsa-miR-106b-5p					
hsa-miR-107					
hsa-miR-10a-3p					
hsa-miR-10a-5p					
hsa-miR-10b-3p					
hsa-miR-10b-5p	hsa-miR-10b-5p	0.01626139	0.0003708	#iDIV/0!	>0.05
hsa-miR-1180-3p					
hsa-miR-122-5p					
hsa-miR-1224-5p					
hsa-miR-1226-3p					
hsa-miR-124-3p					
hsa-miR-1246					
hsa-miR-1255a					
hsa-miR-1255b-5p					
hsa-miR-125a-3p					
hsa-miR-125a-5p	hsa-miR-125a-5p	0.06167705	0.01034344	0.04037803	>0.05
hsa-miR-125b-5p	hsa-miR-125b-5p	0.00032825	0.00046249	#iDIV/0!	>0.05
hsa-miR-126-3p	hsa-miR-126-3p	0.07143553	0.00377239	0.00241965	>0.05
hsa-miR-126-5p					
hsa-miR-1260b					

hsa-miR-1268a					
hsa-miR-1268b					
hsa-miR-127-3p					
hsa-miR-1270					
hsa-miR-1273h-3p					
hsa-miR-1277-3p					
hsa-miR-1277-5p					
hsa-miR-128-3p					
hsa-miR-1284					
hsa-miR-1291					
hsa-miR-1294					
hsa-miR-1296-5p					
hsa-miR-1299					
hsa-miR-1301-3p					
hsa-miR-1304-3p					
hsa-miR-1306-5p					
hsa-miR-1307-3p					
hsa-miR-1307-5p					
hsa-miR-130a-3p					
hsa-miR-130b-3p					
hsa-miR-130b-5p					
hsa-miR-132-3p					
hsa-miR-133a-3p					
hsa-miR-134-5p					
hsa-miR-135a-5p					
hsa-miR-136-3p					
hsa-miR-136-5p					
hsa-miR-139-3p					
hsa-miR-139-5p					
hsa-miR-140-3p					
hsa-miR-140-5p					
hsa-miR-141-3p					
hsa-miR-142-3p	hsa-miR-142-3p	0.00315489	0.00255245	0.00468978	>0.05
hsa-miR-142-5p					
hsa-miR-143-3p					
hsa-miR-143-5p					
hsa-miR-144-3p					
hsa-miR-144-5p					
hsa-miR-145-5p					
hsa-miR-1468-5p					
hsa-miR-146a-3p					
hsa-miR-146a-5p	hsa-miR-146a-5p	0.00119219	0.00084927	0.00181544	>0.05
hsa-miR-146b-3p					

hsa-miR-146b-5p					
hsa-miR-148a-3p					
hsa-miR-148b-3p					
hsa-miR-148b-5p					
hsa-miR-149-5p					
hsa-miR-150-3p					
hsa-miR-150-5p	hsa-miR-150-5p	0.00869422	0.00179029	0.00254674	>0.05
hsa-miR-151a-3p	hsa-miR-151a-3p	4.5579E-05	0.00019013	#iDIV/0!	>0.05
hsa-miR-151a-5p					
hsa-miR-152-3p					
hsa-miR-154-5p					
hsa-miR-155-5p					
hsa-miR-15a-5p					
hsa-miR-15b-3p					
hsa-miR-15b-5p					
hsa-miR-16-2-3p	hsa-miR-16-2-3p	0.00198516	0.00035311	#iDIV/0!	>0.05
hsa-miR-16-5p	hsa-miR-16-5p	0.22838487	0.07345021	0.04082892	<0.01
hsa-miR-17-3p					
hsa-miR-17-5p					
hsa-miR-181a-2-3p					
hsa-miR-181a-3p					
hsa-miR-181a-5p					
hsa-miR-181b-5p					
hsa-miR-181c-3p					
hsa-miR-181c-5p					
hsa-miR-182-5p					
hsa-miR-183-5p					
hsa-miR-184					
hsa-miR-185-3p					
hsa-miR-185-5p					
hsa-miR-186-5p					
hsa-miR-18a-5p					
hsa-miR-1908-5p					
hsa-miR-190a-5p					
hsa-miR-190b					
hsa-miR-191-3p					
hsa-miR-191-5p	hsa-miR-191-5p	0.00137533	0.00086079	0.0022254	>0.05
hsa-miR-192-5p					
hsa-miR-193a-5p					
hsa-miR-193b-5p					
hsa-miR-194-5p					
hsa-miR-195-5p					
hsa-miR-196a-5p					

hsa-miR-196b-5p						
hsa-miR-197-3p						
hsa-miR-197-5p						
hsa-miR-199a-3p	hsa-miR-199a-3p	0.00101183	0.00050359	0.00072762	>0.05	
hsa-miR-199a-5p						
hsa-miR-199b-3p						
hsa-miR-199b-5p						
hsa-miR-19a-3p	hsa-miR-19a-3p	0.01296426	0.00381417	0.00234627	<0.01	
hsa-miR-19b-3p						
hsa-miR-200a-3p						
hsa-miR-200b-3p						
hsa-miR-200c-3p						
hsa-miR-203a						
hsa-miR-204-5p						
hsa-miR-205-5p						
hsa-miR-206						
hsa-miR-20a-5p						
hsa-miR-20b-3p						
hsa-miR-20b-5p						
hsa-miR-21-3p						
hsa-miR-21-5p						
hsa-miR-210-3p						
hsa-miR-2110						
hsa-miR-215-5p						
hsa-miR-22-3p						
hsa-miR-22-5p						
hsa-miR-221-3p						
hsa-miR-221-5p						
hsa-miR-222-3p	hsa-miR-222-3p	0.00052333	0.00078708	#iDIV/0!	>0.05	
hsa-miR-222-5p						
hsa-miR-223-3p						
hsa-miR-223-5p						
hsa-miR-224-5p						
hsa-miR-2277-3p						
hsa-miR-2355-3p						
hsa-miR-23a-3p						
hsa-miR-23a-5p						
hsa-miR-23b-3p						
hsa-miR-23b-5p						
hsa-miR-24-3p						
hsa-miR-25-3p	hsa-miR-25-3p	0.06864934	0.01077911	0.00998553	<0.05	
hsa-miR-25-5p						
hsa-miR-26a-1-3p						

hsa-miR-26a-2-3p					
hsa-miR-26a-5p					
hsa-miR-26b-3p					
hsa-miR-26b-5p					
hsa-miR-27a-3p					
hsa-miR-27a-5p	hsa-miR-27a-5p	0.22879773	0.03846838	0.059109257	>0.05
hsa-miR-27b-3p					
hsa-miR-27b-5p					
hsa-miR-28-3p					
hsa-miR-28-5p					
hsa-miR-296-5p					
hsa-miR-299-5p					
hsa-miR-29a-3p					
hsa-miR-29b-1-5p					
hsa-miR-29b-3p					
hsa-miR-29c-3p					
hsa-miR-29c-5p					
hsa-miR-301a-3p	hsa-miR-301a-3p	5.9416E-05	0.00025332	#iDIV/0!	>0.05
hsa-miR-3074-5p					
hsa-miR-30a-3p					
hsa-miR-30a-5p					
hsa-miR-30b-5p					
hsa-miR-30c-1-3p					
hsa-miR-30c-5p					
hsa-miR-30d-3p					
hsa-miR-30d-5p	hsa-miR-30d-5p	14060781.1	0.00092492	0.00084244	>0.05
hsa-miR-30e-3p					
hsa-miR-30e-5p					
hsa-miR-31-5p					
hsa-miR-3124-5p					
hsa-miR-3131					
hsa-miR-3138					
hsa-miR-3143					
hsa-miR-3158-3p					
hsa-miR-3168					
hsa-miR-3173-5p					
hsa-miR-3195					
hsa-miR-32-3p					
hsa-miR-32-5p					
hsa-miR-320a					
hsa-miR-320b	hsa-miR-320b	0.00080938	6.232E-05	#iDIV/0!	>0.05
hsa-miR-320c					
hsa-miR-320d					

hsa-miR-323a-3p					
hsa-miR-323b-3p					
hsa-miR-324-3p					
hsa-miR-324-5p					
hsa-miR-326					
hsa-miR-328-3p					
hsa-miR-329-3p					
hsa-miR-330-5p					
hsa-miR-331-3p					
hsa-miR-335-3p	hsa-miR-335-3p	0.00082986	0.01341555	#iDIV/0!	>0.05
hsa-miR-335-5p					
hsa-miR-337-3p					
hsa-miR-337-5p					
hsa-miR-338-3p					
hsa-miR-339-3p					
hsa-miR-339-5p					
hsa-miR-33a-5p					
hsa-miR-340-3p					
hsa-miR-340-5p					
hsa-miR-342-3p	hsa-miR-342-3p	0.00073729	0.00058731	7.3522E-05	>0.05
hsa-miR-342-5p					
hsa-miR-345-5p					
hsa-miR-34a-5p					
hsa-miR-34c-5p					
hsa-miR-3605-3p					
hsa-miR-3605-5p					
hsa-miR-361-3p					
hsa-miR-361-5p					
hsa-miR-3613-3p					
hsa-miR-3613-5p					
hsa-miR-3614-5p					
hsa-miR-3615					
hsa-miR-363-3p					
hsa-miR-3653					
hsa-miR-3679-5p					
hsa-miR-369-3p					
hsa-miR-369-5p					
hsa-miR-370-3p					
hsa-miR-373-3p					
hsa-miR-374a-3p					
hsa-miR-374a-5p					
hsa-miR-374b-3p					
hsa-miR-374b-5p					

hsa-miR-375					
hsa-miR-376a-3p					
hsa-miR-376b-3p					
hsa-miR-376b-5p					
hsa-miR-376c-3p					
hsa-miR-377-3p					
hsa-miR-378a-3p	hsa-miR-378a-3p	0.01712169	0.00012684	0.00107996	>0.05
hsa-miR-379-5p					
hsa-miR-381-3p					
hsa-miR-382-3p					
hsa-miR-382-5p					
hsa-miR-3913-5p					
hsa-miR-409-3p					
hsa-miR-409-5p					
hsa-miR-411-5p					
hsa-miR-412-5p					
hsa-miR-421					
hsa-miR-423-3p					
hsa-miR-423-5p					
hsa-miR-424-5p					
hsa-miR-425-3p					
hsa-miR-425-5p					
hsa-miR-429					
hsa-miR-4306					
hsa-miR-431-5p					
hsa-miR-432-5p					
hsa-miR-4433-3p					
hsa-miR-4433b-3p					
hsa-miR-4433b-5p					
hsa-miR-4435					
hsa-miR-4446-3p					
hsa-miR-450a-5p					
hsa-miR-4511					
hsa-miR-451a	hsa-miR-451a	0.12567661	0.02106744	0.02554043	<0.01
hsa-miR-4532					
hsa-miR-454-3p					
hsa-miR-454-5p					
hsa-miR-4668-5p					
hsa-miR-4714-3p					
hsa-miR-4732-3p					
hsa-miR-4732-5p					
hsa-miR-4755-3p					
hsa-miR-4772-3p					

hsa-miR-4792					
hsa-miR-483-3p					
hsa-miR-483-5p					
hsa-miR-484					
hsa-miR-485-3p	hsa-miR-485-3p				
hsa-miR-485-5p					
hsa-miR-486-3p	hsa-miR-486-3p				
hsa-miR-486-5p	hsa-miR-486-5p	0.0154023	0.01123061	0.00682534	>0.05
hsa-miR-487a-5p					
hsa-miR-487b-3p					
hsa-miR-487b-5p					
hsa-miR-491-5p					
hsa-miR-493-3p					
hsa-miR-493-5p					
hsa-miR-494-3p					
hsa-miR-496					
hsa-miR-499a-5p					
hsa-miR-500a-3p					
hsa-miR-501-3p					
hsa-miR-5010-5p					
hsa-miR-502-3p					
hsa-miR-503-5p					
hsa-miR-504-3p					
hsa-miR-504-5p					
hsa-miR-505-3p					
hsa-miR-505-5p					
hsa-miR-508-3p					
hsa-miR-5090					
hsa-miR-5187-5p					
hsa-miR-518b					
hsa-miR-532-3p					
hsa-miR-532-5p					
hsa-miR-542-3p					
hsa-miR-542-5p					
hsa-miR-543					
hsa-miR-548a-3p					
hsa-miR-548am-5p					
hsa-miR-548ay-5p					
hsa-miR-548j-5p					
hsa-miR-548o-5p					
hsa-miR-551b-3p					
hsa-miR-552-5p					
hsa-miR-5586-5p					

hsa-miR-574-3p					
hsa-miR-574-5p					
hsa-miR-576-5p					
hsa-miR-582-3p					
hsa-miR-582-5p					
hsa-miR-584-5p	hsa-miR-584-5p				
hsa-miR-589-5p					
hsa-miR-590-3p					
hsa-miR-598-3p					
hsa-miR-625-3p					
hsa-miR-625-5p					
hsa-miR-628-3p					
hsa-miR-628-5p					
hsa-miR-629-5p					
hsa-miR-641					
hsa-miR-642a-5p					
hsa-miR-6511a-3p					
hsa-miR-6514-5p					
hsa-miR-652-3p					
hsa-miR-652-5p					
hsa-miR-654-3p					
hsa-miR-660-5p					
					>0.05
hsa-miR-664a-3p	hsa-miR-664a-3p	4.0487E-05	8.9544E-05	0.00068792	(0.076)
hsa-miR-664a-5p					
hsa-miR-664b-5p					
hsa-miR-671-3p					
hsa-miR-671-5p					
hsa-miR-6721-5p					
hsa-miR-6740-5p					
hsa-miR-6741-3p					
hsa-miR-6741-5p					
hsa-miR-6759-5p					
hsa-miR-676-3p					
hsa-miR-6793-5p					
hsa-miR-6805-5p					
hsa-miR-6851-3p					
hsa-miR-6852-5p					
hsa-miR-6858-5p					
hsa-miR-6859-5p					
hsa-miR-6866-3p					
hsa-miR-6893-3p					
hsa-miR-7-5p					

hsa-miR-744-3p					
hsa-miR-744-5p					
hsa-miR-760					
hsa-miR-769-5p					
hsa-miR-7976					
hsa-miR-874-3p					
hsa-miR-874-5p					
hsa-miR-875-5p					
hsa-miR-889-3p					
hsa-miR-9-5p					
					>0.05
hsa-miR-92a-3p	hsa-miR-92a-3p	0.02290708	0.00856341	0.01964535	(0.09)
hsa-miR-92b-3p					
hsa-miR-93-3p					
hsa-miR-93-5p					
hsa-miR-941					
hsa-miR-942-5p					
hsa-miR-95-3p					
hsa-miR-96-5p					
hsa-miR-98-5p					
hsa-miR-99a-5p					
hsa-miR-99b-3p					
hsa-miR-99b-5p	hsa-miR-99b-5p				

Supplementary Table 2. A. KEGG analysis of validated targets (Tarbase v7) of hsa-miR-19a-3p, hsa-miR-16-5p and hsa-miR-451a. B. KEGG analysis of validated targets (Tarbase v7) of hsa-miR-25-3p.

KEGG pathway	p-value	Genes	miRNAs
Proteoglycans in cancer	1,63E-18	88	3
Prion diseases	1,48E-11	13	2
Viral carcinogenesis	4,65E-10	82	3
TGF-beta signaling pathway	1,08E-09	40	3
Prostate cancer	2,25E-08	50	3
Signaling pathways regulating pluripotency of stem cells	4,91E-08	63	3
Fatty acid biosynthesis	8,57E-08	4	2
Hepatitis B	8,57E-08	63	3
Adherens junction	1,81E-07	38	3
Hippo signaling pathway	2,14E-07	56	3
Glioma	4,19E-07	33	3
Cell cycle	5,60E-06	57	3
Colorectal cancer	6,87E-06	33	3
Pancreatic cancer	6,87E-06	35	3
Chronic myeloid leukemia	7,75E-06	37	3
Oocyte meiosis	1,04E-05	48	2
RNA transport	2,25E-05	71	2
Endometrial cancer	2,25E-05	28	3
Bacterial invasion of epithelial cells	2,64E-05	35	3
Estrogen signaling pathway	3,11E-05	43	3
Protein processing in endoplasmic reticulum	4,65E-05	70	2
p53 signaling pathway	6,95E-05	36	2
FoxO signaling pathway	7,53E-05	58	3
Shigellosis	0,000124162	32	3
Glycosaminoglycan biosynthesis - keratan sulfate	0,000189301	6	2
Melanoma	0,00019353	33	3
Non-small cell lung cancer	0,000275343	27	3
Sphingolipid signaling pathway	0,00034239	51	3
Prolactin signaling pathway	0,00034239	34	3
Bladder cancer	0,000351011	22	3
Pathways in cancer	0,00041622	137	3
Central carbon metabolism in cancer	0,000588651	32	3
Small cell lung cancer	0,000725539	39	3
mTOR signaling pathway	0,0016319	29	3
Neurotrophin signaling pathway	0,0016319	51	3
Progesterone-mediated oocyte maturation	0,0016319	40	3
Renal cell carcinoma	0,0016319	32	3

Thyroid cancer	0,002118072	14	3
Ubiquitin mediated proteolysis	0,002416532	54	3
Other types of O-glycan biosynthesis	0,002900794	11	2
Insulin signaling pathway	0,003537148	56	3
Acute myeloid leukemia	0,004955279	27	3
AMPK signaling pathway	0,007676192	50	3
Dorso-ventral axis formation	0,00882073	15	2
Thyroid hormone signaling pathway	0,009658482	48	3
Apoptosis	0,009930241	35	3
Ribosome biogenesis in eukaryotes	0,012270945	36	2
Type II diabetes mellitus	0,015730768	21	3
Adrenergic signaling in cardiomyocytes	0,015770149	48	3
Citrate cycle (TCA cycle)	0,022554076	13	2
TNF signaling pathway	0,022554076	44	3
Glycosaminoglycan biosynthesis - chondroitin sulfate / dermatan sulfate	0,026763341	7	2
Fatty acid metabolism	0,028305822	14	2
ErbB signaling pathway	0,030370317	32	3
Hepatitis C	0,044397994	49	3
Focal adhesion	0,048375962	71	3

KEGG pathway	p-value	Genes	miRNAs
Prion diseases	1,08E-23	3	1
Lysine degradation	4,51E-07	10	1
Cell cycle	4,58E-06	30	1
Viral carcinogenesis	4,58E-06	30	1
Valine, leucine and isoleucine biosynthesis	0,000177058	2	1
Adherens junction	0,000177058	13	1
Chronic myeloid leukemia	0,000232027	17	1
p53 signaling pathway	0,000815916	15	1
Proteoglycans in cancer	0,00087798	24	1
FoxO signaling pathway	0,001106241	24	1
Endometrial cancer	0,001106241	11	1
Pathways in cancer	0,001498555	42	1
Colorectal cancer	0,001571138	11	1
Thyroid cancer	0,001696283	7	1
Hippo signaling pathway	0,002328827	20	1
Prostate cancer	0,002328827	17	1
Melanoma	0,002340632	12	1
Hepatitis B	0,003135443	23	1
2-Oxocarboxylic acid metabolism	0,004218726	4	1
Regulation of actin cytoskeleton	0,006786458	26	1
Bladder cancer	0,006786458	10	1

HTLV-I infection	0,011958331	34	1
MAPK signaling pathway	0,014001276	28	1
Protein processing in endoplasmic reticulum	0,014001276	22	1
Estrogen signaling pathway	0,014001276	12	1
Glioma	0,014001276	11	1
Non-small cell lung cancer	0,017503177	9	1
Oocyte meiosis	0,021253461	15	1
Dorso-ventral axis formation	0,025665577	7	1
Thyroid hormone signaling pathway	0,025665577	19	1
TGF-beta signaling pathway	0,033266756	9	1
Small cell lung cancer	0,039796579	13	1

Supplementary Figure S1. Histogram of hydrodynamic diameter of extracellular vesicles observed through DLS using a Zetasizer Nano SZ system (Malvern Instruments, UK).

Supplementary Figure S2. Isolated extracellular vesicles observed on transmission electron microscopy (120x)